

Code Inspection Checklist

Reviewer:

Code:

- Is the code properly formatted?

- Are variables clearly and succinctly named?

- Is the code split up into functions and files of appropriate lengths?

- Is code understandability aided by suitable comments?

- Are there no repetitive elements that should be refactored?

- Are there no hard-coded values that should be either named constants or configurable parameters?

- Does the software check for bad input (defensive programming)?

- Are libraries employed where useful, but not unnecessarily?

- Does the design make good use of encapsulation and abstraction?

- Is the user interface easy to understand and use?

- Is there sufficient documentation to allow an external person to use and modify the software?

- Can the program be automated?

- Are there mechanisms for verifying correctness? (Error messages, logging, unit tests...)